

**YUSUFJAN QIZIQ SHAKARJANOV'S ROLE OF IN THE UZBEK
THEATER**

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Abstract: The service of Yusufjan Khevan Shakarjanov in the development of traditional Uzbek theater is incomparable. It will be discussed below.

Key words: interesting, troupe, repertoire.

One of those who made a great contribution to the creation of Uzbek Soviet art, a famous representative of folk art, is Yusufjan qiziq Shakarjanov. He was born in 1869 in the family of Shakarjon, a tanner, and Chevar Tajibibi, who lived in the city of Margilon.

Yusufjan lived an interesting 90 years, 83 of which he devoted to art. In his blessed life, he saw three different regimes (Khanate era, colonial era and Soviet power), traveled the path of great creativity, and experienced a lot of events. His childhood years, especially his first creative steps, took place during the reign of Khudoyor Khan (1862-1876), the last king of Kokand. There were male and female troupes of amateurs in the palace of Khudoyor Khan, the men's troupe was led by Zakir Eshan, and the female troupe was led by famous amateurs named Iqlim Dodho. Although these troupes served in the palace, their repertoire and the social essence of their work were completely folk-oriented. That is why they entered the people as soon as the khanate collapsed. Talented Yusufjon did not miss the attention of the Zakir Eshan troupe. In 1876, the famous enthusiast Sa'di Makhsum (1809-1889) who saw Yusufjan's interest in a teahouse with his acquaintances Matholiq and Artiqboy, took them as his apprentices.

The theater of amateurs gave a show based on a pre-planned theme and story. That is why the actor played a leading and decisive role in this theater. Every hobbyist had to go to a certain school in order to master the art of hobby and raise his skills to a professional level. There are two different methods of raising a hobbyist. Although the same teachers take their students with them and sometimes entrust them with some small roles, they do not have lessons, do not give them special exercises, sometimes give a short explanation, definition, advice, warning and limited by approval. The student mainly followed the path of observing the games and movements of other great artists, carefully studying them, and mastering their repertoire.

Yusufjan qiziq played in the Zakir Eshan troupe under the guidance and patronage of Sa'di Makhsum for ten years. He traveled through the valley of Fergana, there was no town or village that he did not see. Yusufjan was completely charmed by the hard life of entertainers and hobbyists, but noble in its content and purpose, romantic in its abundance of adventures. During these years, Yusufjan perfectly mastered the repertoire of the art of humor and laughter, performance skills, and the rules of staging. He started his career from small, supporting roles and rose to the level of a director. At the same time, he successfully combined all the "secrets" and concepts, types and methods of the national dance and became a mature dancer. In the traditional theater, music, dance and circus were so intertwined that they could not be separated from each other. That is why it was obligatory for those interested to be well informed about these arts. The students were also taught the art of dancing, and sometimes they were called separately to the maraka. Yusufjan also mastered Fergana dance series called "Katta Oyin" and "Khona Bazm" and danced for several years and pleased the people. He did not limit himself to knowing only the movements of the dances, but also learned their circle and drum techniques very well.

According to brother Yusufjan's confession, he knew about one hundred and fifty dance methods in the late 1880s. In 1892, after Zakir Eshon died suddenly in

Osh, the troupe was divided into small groups. Yusufjan aka, who had already received the title of "qiziq", came to Margilon and formed a good troupe of well-known comedians, musicians, and khafiz in the city and its surroundings. Yusufjan served with his interesting troupe until the Soviet era in folk dances and dances, sometimes in Russian and Uzbek circus associations. During these years, the satirical comedies, taqlids, funny stories, dances and askiyas, learned from his teachers, are in the first place in the repertoire of Yusufjan qiziq, especially comedies called "criticism" and "imitation" in the activities of Yusufjan qiziq and the gang he led. With the artist's troupe, "Child education", "Bride dropped off", "Zarkokil", "Mozor", "Mudarris", "Dukhtarbozlik", "Shepherd boy", "Kalandars", " performed dozens of traditional comedies such as "Gambling", "Capricorn", "Being a Husband", "Mamayusuf". Since these comedies are based on badiha without text, they are freely staged and performed. In general, Yusufjon tried to interpret any interesting play in the spirit of the times. Yusufzhan qiziq has always played the lead role. He is a sheikh ("Mozor"), a chairman ("Zarkokil"), a mudarris ("Mudarris"), a teacher ("Bola ukitish"), a judge ("Becoming a husband"), an elder ("yelpib oturisin"), father ("Mamayusuf"), son-in-law ("The bride brought down"), doctor ("Chinese doctor") with excellent skill. It is worth mentioning.

The years Yusufjan worked in the Mullaboy Mansurov circus, which he himself was very active in organizing, showed good activity. He performed in Khiva, Bukhara, Turkestan, and Avliyotas as part of this troupe and performed the art of Ferghana's amateurs. During these years, Yusufjon grew up interestingly as a performer, a businessman, a businessman, and a teacher. his passion for horses grew stronger.

In 1905-1908, Yusufjan traveled to Iran, India, Afghanistan and Kashgar with a troupe of interesting musicians, singers and dancers. During these years, in addition to organizational work and artistic leadership of the troupe, he personally mastered new aspects of the art of laughter and dance and sharpened his skills. Although he did not know languages well, he made Persian, Hindi, Afghan,

Uyghur and Chinese people laugh, gave them aesthetic pleasure and pleasure. Not only did he demonstrate the music, dance and interest of his people, but at the same time he studied the culture, art, and traditions of the neighboring peoples. Now he was trained in all aspects, matured, an artist seen by the world. That's why Yusufjan interestingly started to enjoy the Iranian, Afghan, Indian and Uyghur dances, which he studied abroad, and did not limit himself to the national repertoire. He weaved dozens of funny stories and anecdotes based on the countless incidents he experienced on his travels. They passed by word of mouth and became the artistic property of the people.

In 1908, the artist gave artistic pleasure and pleasure to the Russian audience in cooperation with Russian circus artists in St. Petersburg. At the same time, he managed to watch Russian classical ballets. Enjoying advanced Russian art and creative cooperation with its representatives helped Yusufjan's creative work to grow more ideologically. He bravely and mercilessly whipped the representatives of the exploiting class and openly promoted democratic ideas. It is probably for this reason that both local officials and korchalans, as well as the colonial administration, recognized the interesting talent of Yusufjan, who gained a great reputation among the masses of working people, who could make a great contribution to the development of national art, and gave him the conditions They tried to humiliate him by calling him a "clown", let alone creating one. As a result, in an interesting old fashion, he performed and played only at weddings, parties, and home parties, and could not fully demonstrate his talent and capabilities. Only after the Great October Revolution, Yusufjan found his dignity, was recognized as an outstanding representative of folk art, and had all the conditions and opportunities to glorify his talent, knowledge, experience, and skill.

Having mastered all the qualities of the art of Fergana clown. Yusufjan qiziq, who developed it on a large scale, was truly rich and productive during the Soviet period. The artist participated very actively and enthusiastically in the reviews, competitions, Olympiads, decades held in different periods, in different circles, in

the construction of public facilities, in the councils, congresses, holidays, parties that are held several times a year. . During the Soviet era, he worked honestly for the sake of the Uzbek people, who had a happy life and a bright future.

Yusufjan is a great artist who deeply grasps all the wealth and virtues of the Kokand school of curiosity. He has a brilliant creativity, like famous amateurs who passed before him. Yusufjan is an equal weight, great and bright figure in interesting theater, dance, pantomime, imitation, usul, askiya, and organization. Yusufjan was not only aware of interesting art forms, but mastered them perfectly. It was such a priceless treasure, a talisman that, starting with Hamza, they began to open it and study it. 34 comedies recorded by Yusufjon qiziq, dozens of funny stories, muqallid, method and tunes, countless interviews held with him on various topics of folk art became the property of the people, enriching the cultural treasury with masterpieces.

Yusufjan taught how to sort and use the interesting past tense. As a result, "Interests began to speak "cleaner"" during the years of Yusufjan's struggle against interesting printers, Hamza's "Tragedy of Loshman" (in the role of ellikboshi), "The Punishment of Slanderers" (in the role of Sultan pianist), the third part of "Tragedies of Ferghana" He successfully participated in the dramas "Makom Shahido" (in the role of Abdullajon Mahsum), "Doy, workers", "Capital". His service was especially great in the concert program. "I wrote funny stories about the fight against the oppressors. I also used to imitate the dances of the peoples of Central Asia.

Yusufjan visited a number of large cities of the Soviet Union with the interesting Muhyiddin Kori-Yakubov troupe and played music. Everywhere, among others, they appreciated his interesting art. For example, the "Communist" newspaper published in Baku wrote: "Yusuf left an impression on the audience to an interesting extent. Yusufjan, one of the Azerbaijani amateurs, shows interesting "Big House" movements.

In 1936-40, Yusufjon participated in the concerts of the Uzbek State Philharmonic, encouraged young artists, organized them, and gave them creative inspiration. In May 1937, Yusufjan made an interesting and important contribution to the preparation and holding of the first decade of Uzbek art in Moscow. In staging the two-part production (libretto by K. Yashin) entitled "Art of the Uzbek people" ("Sayil" and "Kolkhoz tuyi"), it took a lot of work to collect 15 interested people, guide and mentor them. , took the initiative. In the play, he played the role of the chairman (in the comedy "Zarkokil"), together with Aka Bukhor Zakirov, Mirshokhid Mirokilov, Kamil Qori Kulijonov, he performed a musical comic play called "Sokiy", Erka Qori Karimov, Mamayunus Tillaboev, Aka Bukhor Zakirov, Mamajon Makhsum argued with the Mirzaakhmedovs.

When the Great Patriotic War started, Yusufjan Shakarjanov was 72 years old. During the years of the war, when the people suffered a great calamity, he didn't sit idly by because of his old age. On the contrary, father Yusufjan's eyes flashed with fire, his anger boiled over the enemy, and he looked for ways to raise the spirit of the people. Laughter was one of the means of raising the spirits of the people working night after night and day after day behind the front, strengthening their confidence in the inevitability of victory over the enemy. Belief in good intentions and the power of laughter led Yusufjan to the Yangiyol Musical Drama and Comedy Theater (1941-42), then to the Uzbek State Circus (1942-45).

Together with Okhunjon Khuzurzhanov in the theater and Karim Zarifov and Ibrayim Khuzun Teshaboev in the circus, he made the audience laugh by showing unique laughter, entrées and reprises mocking the old world bullies and mocking the German Nazis. Despite the fact that the old artist was provided with a personal pension in the years after the war, he did not rest. He created new folk ensembles, took part in concert programs, sometimes joined the troupes of folk musicians. During this period, as an amateur, he mainly performed small-scale curiosities, mentoring young comedy enthusiasts. Also, he spent a lot of effort and energy to

make art critics enjoy the legacy of his art, knowledge, and rich experience, to organize and develop curiosity.

In particular, in 1958-59, the activity of Yusufjon Qiziq was rich. Yusufjan took his young student Okhunjon Khuzurjonov to Tashkent in the days of intensive preparations for the decade of Uzbek literature and art in Moscow. Although he was 90 years old, this old man, whose back is not bent and whose eyes are shining like young men, did not stop. He hung out with his friends and students in Tashkent, went to theaters, and watched the circus. He visited the school of choreography. He gave concerts on the pop stage. Most importantly, he appeared in the main role in the short film-concert called "songs are flying" This was his gift to Moscow. And Moscow sent him with the Order of the Red Banner of Labor on his chest.

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